

Table 1. Effects of soil amendments on rice yield. Uttar Pradesh, India, 1987-92.

Soil amendment	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)						Six-year average			
	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	Rice		Wheat	
							Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Increase over control (%)	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Increase over control (%)
Control	0.9	2.2	2.8	3.1	3.5	3.8	2.7	–	1.2	–
Gypsum (6 t ha ⁻¹)	1.8	3.1	3.5	3.8	4.1	4.3	3.4	25.9	2.0	66.7
Gypsum (9 t ha ⁻¹)	2.2	3.4	3.8	4.1	4.5	4.8	3.8	40.7	2.4	100.0
Gypsum (12 t ha ⁻¹)	2.6	3.8	4.2	4.6	4.9	5.1	4.2	55.6	2.9	141.7
Pyrite (2 t ha ⁻¹)	1.3	2.5	3.0	3.3	3.7	3.9	3.0	11.1	1.7	41.7
Pyrite (3 t ha ⁻¹)	1.6	2.9	3.1	3.4	3.8	4.0	3.1	14.8	1.9	58.3
Pyrite (4 t ha ⁻¹)	2.5	3.5	3.9	4.3	4.5	4.6	3.9	44.4	2.5	108.3
Mud press (6 t ha ⁻¹)	1.5	2.7	3.1	3.4	3.7	3.8	3.0	11.1	1.7	41.7
Mud press (12 t ha ⁻¹)	1.7	3.1	3.4	3.8	4.1	4.3	3.4	25.9	2.0	66.7
FYM ^a (20 t ha ⁻¹)	1.4	2.7	2.9	3.3	3.6	3.9	3.0	11.1	1.5	25.0
FYM (10 t) + pyrite (2 t ha ⁻¹)	2.2	3.2	3.6	3.9	4.2	4.4	3.6	33.3	2.0	66.7
FYM (10 t) + mud press (6 t ha ⁻¹)	2.4	3.3	3.7	4.1	4.3	4.5	3.7	37.0	2.2	83.3
SEM (±)	0.12	0.05	0.07	0.06	0.09	0.016	–	–	–	–
LSD (5%)	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.5	–	–	–	–

^aFYM = farmyard manure.

Table 2. Physicochemical properties of surface soil (0-15 cm)^a after 6 yr of experimentation. Uttar Pradesh, India, 1987-92.

Treatment	pH (1:2 soil-water ratio)	EC (dSm ⁻¹) (1:2 soil-water ratio)	CEC (c mol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹)	Exchangeable cations (c mol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹)				Exchangeable sodium percentage
				Na ⁺	K	Ca ⁺⁺	Mg ⁺⁺	
Control	8.2	0.40	12.0	0.58	0.19	5.27	1.27	4.83
Gypsum (6 t ha ⁻¹)	8.1	0.36	12.1	0.42	0.12	7.00	1.20	3.50
Gypsum (9 t ha ⁻¹)	7.8	0.33	12.0	0.41	0.11	7.13	1.00	3.45
Gypsum (12 t ha ⁻¹)	7.3	0.33	12.0	0.40	0.11	7.47	1.13	3.13
Pyrite (2 t ha ⁻¹)	8.2	0.36	12.1	0.49	0.16	6.80	1.27	3.95
Pyrite (3 t ha ⁻¹)	8.1	0.34	12.1	0.43	0.14	7.00	1.10	3.58
Pyrite (4 t ha ⁻¹)	7.8	0.35	12.2	0.40	0.12	7.10	1.00	3.28
Mud press (6 t ha ⁻¹)	8.1	0.35	12.1	0.40	0.13	6.73	1.00	3.28
Mud press (12 t ha ⁻¹)	7.8	0.29	11.8	0.39	0.12	7.20	1.27	3.31
FYM (20 t ha ⁻¹)	7.7	0.30	12.3	0.42	0.19	6.13	0.93	3.44
FYM (10 t) + pyrite (2 t ha ⁻¹)	8.0	0.33	12.0	0.39	0.19	6.67	1.00	3.22
FYM (10 t) + mud press (6 t ha ⁻¹)	7.7	0.32	12.1	0.38	0.16	7.47	0.86	3.22
SEM (±)		0.02		0.03	0.03	0.29	0.13	–
LSD (5%)		ns ^b		0.09	ns	0.84	ns	–

^aThe Initial values were pH 9.4-9.8, EC 6.9 dS m⁻¹, CEC 12.4 cmol(p⁺) kg⁻¹, and ESP 22.6. ^bns = not significant.

Applying FYM at 10 t ha⁻¹ in combination with pyrite at 2 t ha⁻¹ or gypsum at 6 t ha⁻¹ resulted in comparable yields. The amendments were effective in this order: gypsum > pyrite > mud press > FYM.

Wheat yield averaged 1.2 t ha⁻¹ in the control treatment (Table 1). Maximum yield increase was observed with gypsum application at 12 t ha⁻¹ and minimum with FYM at 20 t ha⁻¹. The pattern of effectiveness of soil amendments in the wheat crop was similar to that in the rice crop.

After 6 yr, the pH and exchangeable sodium percentage in the control and treated plots were appreciably reduced, and the level of amendment applied was reflected in this reduction (Table 2). Besides the amendments, the rice - wheat cropping sequence has a profound influence on soil improvement, as reflected in the yield levels from year 1 to year 6. Gypsum alone or gypsum with FYM outperformed pyrite. ■

Crop management

Use of deepwater varietal mixtures to minimize hydrological risk in basin lands of Bihar, India

M. M. Sinha, A. Kumar, N. Chaudhary, Rajendra Agricultural University, Bihar Agricultural Research Institute, Mithapur, Patna 800001, India

Chours (basin lands) are low-lying fields of variable shape and size having poor or no drainage. Crop production depends mainly on the unpredictable monsoon rainfall. Drought or flooding of varying durations

and intensities are the main hydrological constraints to rice productivity.

Cultivating mixtures of deepwater rice (DWR) is a prevalent practice in chaur. The varieties used have almost identical morphological characters and are highly adapted to sowing and transplanting conditions in the area. We studied the submergence tolerance of DWR varieties Darmi and Jagar under different hydrological conditions.

Five samples of 100 panicles each were collected randomly from deepwater rice-fields (200 cm maximum water depth) cropped with mixtures of Darmi and Jagar during 1990 kharif in chaur. The area was stratified into 50-100, 100-150, and 150-200 cm water depths. Based on kernel color and panicle characteristics, samples from each water regime were classified into three—Darmi, Jagar, and “others.”

Pregerminated seeds of Darmi and Jagar were sown 5 cm apart in five trays filled with soil on 12 Jun 1991. The trays with 14-d-old seedlings were completely submerged in a pond for 7 d with 30 cm of water above the tip of the seedling. On the 10th day of the recovery period, survival count and phenotypic scoring for submergence tolerance were done. The IRR standard scoring system was used; a low score indicates good tolerance.

Table 1. Number of panicles of Darmi, Jagar, and others per sample of 100 panicles, collected from three water depths. Vaishali, Bihar, India.

Sample	Water regimes								
	50-100 cm			100-150 cm			150-200 cm		
	Jagar	Darmi	Others	Jagar	Darmi	Others	Jagar	Darmi	Others
1	52	45	3	34	56	10	21	77	2
2	51	36	13	41	51	8	33	61	6
3	40	50	10	28	63	9	48	50	2
4	49	35	16	40	54	6	26	66	8
5	56	40	4	30	59	11	43	54	3
Total	248	206	46	173	283	44	181	307	21
Av	49.6	41.2	9.2	34.6	56.6	8.8	36.2	61.4	4.2

Table 2. Submergence tolerance scores of Darmi and Jagar. Bihar, India.

Variety	Tray 1	Tray 2	Tray 3	Tray 4	Tray 5	Av
Darmi	7	6	8	6	7	6.8
Jagar	8	9	9	9	8	8.6

Among samples collected from the 50-100 cm water regime, Jagar had more panicles (49.6%) than Darmi (41.2%), suggesting that Jagar was the better adapted cultivar with a greater number of effective tillers.

Among samples obtained from the lower niches of the chaur, Darmi had higher panicle number (56.6 and 61.4%) in the 100-1.50 and 150-200 cm water regimes compared with Jagar, which had 34.5 and 36.2%, respectively (Table 1). This indi-

cates that Darmi was better adapted to deep water than was Jagar.

Darmi had better submergence tolerance (av 6.8) than Jagar (av 8.6) (Table 2). This suggests that Darmi possesses genes that make it suitable for deepwater areas.

Developing DWR varietal mixtures with different levels of submergence tolerance but similar agronomic characters could be one way of minimizing hydrological constraints to growing rice in rainfed low-lying areas. ■

Effect of transplanting times on hybrid rice in Haryana, India

H. Om, Rice Research Station (RRS), Kaul 132021; S. K. Katyal, CCS Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar 125004; S. D. Dhiman and A. Singh, RRS, Kaul, India

We evaluated the performance of newly developed hybrids in India with respect to staggered planting. The field study involved four transplanting dates (15 Jun, 25 Jun, 5 Jul, and 25 Jul) and four genotypes (hybrids ORI 161, PMS2A/IR31802, and PMS01A/PR106 and check variety HKR126) and was conducted during the 1993-94 wet seasons at RRS, Kaul. Soil was clay loam, with pH 8.2, low available N, but high available P and K.

The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with four replications; planting dates were main plots and varieties were

subplots. Plant spacing was 20 × 15 cm. The crop was fertilized with 150 kg N, 26.4 kg P, and 5.75 kg Zn ha⁻¹, with N applied in three equal splits: at transplanting, active tillering, and panicle initiation. Thirty-day-

old seedlings were transplanted in all dates except in the 25 Jul 1993 planting, where 40-d-old seedlings were used.

Highest grain yields were obtained when the genotypes were transplanted on 25 Jun

Effect of transplanting time and genotype on grain yield and harvest index. Kaul, India. 1993-94.

Treatment	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)			Harvest index		Productivity (kg d ⁻¹)		Spikelet sterility (%)	
	1993	1994	Mean	1993	1994	1993	1994	1993	1994
<i>Time of transplanting</i>									
15 Jun	7.2	6.8	7.0	0.51	0.50	46.5	51.0	26.2	27.6
25 Jun	7.9	7.5	7.7	0.54	0.53	51.2	57.1	20.4	23.4
5 Jul	7.6	7.2	7.4	0.53	0.52	50.9	54.6	22.1	25.4
25 Jul	5.5	4.2	4.9	0.46	0.41	41.9	32.1	28.8	37.9
LSD (0.05)	0.4	0.3	-	0.01	0.02	-	-	2.1	1.8
<i>Genotypes</i>									
ORI 161	7.8	7.4	7.6	0.54	0.52	52.9	56.5	19.2	24.4
PMS2 A/IR31802	7.3	6.6	7.0	0.52	0.49	49.1	49.8	25.3	29.7
PMS10 A/PR106	6.3	5.8	6.1	0.48	0.45	42.4	43.7	30.1	33.9
HKR106	6.9	6.1	6.5	0.50	0.49	47.3	46.4	23.5	27.6
LSD (0.05)	0.2	0.2	-	0.01	0.01	-	-	2.0	2.0